

OUTGASSING FROM STAINLESS STEEL UNDER IMPACT IN UHV

R.A.Nevshupa*, J.L. de Segovia,

Instituto de Fisica Aplicada, CETEF "L. Torres Quevedo", CSIC, C/Serrano, 144,

Madrid E-28006, Spain.

Abstract

A study of outgassing by impacting surfaces in ultra high vacuum using mass spectrometry is presented. The substrate, which receives the impact, is a stainless steel AISI 304 sheet. The impacting surface is a carbon chromium ball. Impacts were performed at energies of 3.36 mJ and 9.8 mJ. The average pressure increases over 20 impacts for the first desorption peak in the ultra high vacuum system were 1.0×10^{-9} mbar and 1.9×10^{-10} mbar for the high and low energy impacts respectively. Hydrogen was the main desorbed species with traces of methane. A significant reduction of the pressure intensity increase was always observed after the first impact. Experiments performed by exposing the sample surface to deuterated water at a pressure of 6×10^{-8} mbar for 10 min did not show any D₂O, DHO, DO, D₂ or O₂ desorption. Optical microscopy and atomic force microscopy of the surface subject to impact revealed regions of intense plastic deformation as well as the occurrence of craters. We conclude from these experiments that desorption under mechanical impact in ultra high vacuum comes from the release of hydrogen dissolved in the bulk of the AISI 304 steel substrate. The contribution of adsorbed species to outgassing is negligible.

Keywords: ***outgassing, stainless steel, impact, deuterated water.***

* Corresponding author. e-mail: nevshupa@mail.ru. Present address: Mechanical Engineering Laboratory, Plasticity and Forming Division, 1-2 Namiki, Tsukuba, Ibaraki, 305-8564, Japan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mechanical stimulated outgassing (MSO) produced by friction between moving parts in UHV systems is one of the most important technological problems affecting the manufacturing of devices and components in electronic industry. The phenomenon limits the lowest attainable pressure in UHV and XHV systems and is one of the main sources of hydrocarbons and carbon oxide [1-6]. To understand this phenomenon a significant number of experiments has been performed by testing the whole device [3-6] or simple samples [2,7-13]. A first approximation to the phenomenon involves the determination of the desorbed gases as a function of the contact load and relative speeds between moving parts and the development of an empirical model, which could be applied to real situations. The second aspect is related to the study of fundamental dependencies and basic phenomena resulting in MSO. According to Ishikawa and Yoshimura [13] the mechanical interaction between solids can be classified in the following processes: (i) tension and compression, (ii) sliding and (iii) impact. It should be noted that the second and the third processes also includes tension and compression. While outgassing due to the first two processes has been studied [2-13], the impact phenomenon has not been investigated so extensively [13]. In studying the outgassing by impact there is the benefit of a good control of the energy density released within the contact area during the impact. Plastic deformation of soft materials occurs on the surface more than in the bulk and it is sufficiently homogeneous that is similar to the case of friction. Deformation under tension-compression, however, concentrates in zones of the bulk where the stress exceeds the threshold.

There are three possible sources contributing to the outgassing rate: (i) desorption from the surfaces involved in the impact, (ii) diffusion of dissolved gases from the bulk and (iii) tribochemical induced reactions. Although the phenomenon of MSO was described for the first time in the earlier sixties [14], several basic aspects still remain not understood. Thus,

the main aim of the present preliminary work has been to study the desorption of gases during the impact and to investigate the origin of the desorbed gases.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The experiments were performed in a stainless steel UHV system already described [1]. The sample is a sheet of 15x15 mm² squares of AISI 304 type stainless steel. Prior to introduce in the system, the sample was polished with 6 μm diamond paste and then thoroughly ultrasonic cleaned with acetone and propanol. The impacting surface, the indenter, was a ball of a ball bearing of carbon chromium steel with a diameter of 3.15 mm. The balanced impacting device consisted of a lever, with the longer arm situated in UHV region and the shorter one in the atmospheric side, see Fig.1. The lever can rotate around the lever pin and it is mounted in two ball bearing devices. This allows a slight tilting of the level around the axis of the ball bearings. The lever is welded to a flexible and sensible bellows to minimise the resistant force over the arms of the balance when tilting or impacting force are configured. Details of the construction can be seen in Ref. [1]. The indent ball is mounted at the end of the long arm and keeps normal to the surface during impact. The lever is not at equilibrium because the arms have different lengths and masses. Thus, to perform impacts the short arm of the lever can be pushed down using additional weights. By removing the balance force the lever falls toward the sample and impacts it with a well defined energy that is pre-set by the tilt angle. The momentum of rotation of the unbalanced lever is determined by loading the short arm with known masses. Neglecting resistance in the ball bearings and bellows, the impact energy is determined by the work required to push down the short arm of the lever:

$$E_i = m_e g \Delta h,$$

where Δh is the height with respect to the mass centre. The impact energy can be adjusted by changing Δh .

Both total and partial pressures were measured during the impact of the sample. The experimental chamber is attached to the pumping system via a small orifice with a well-defined conductance that permits to determine the outgassing rate during the impact by recording the pressure signal simultaneously with the ion gauge and mass spectrometer. Residual pressure in the system after degassing and bake-out was of 1.5×10^{-8} mbar

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before performing any impact experiment, the outgassing rate from the lever device under motion but without impacting the sample surface was determined. The pressure increase due to the motion of the lever without impacting the sample was in the range from 2.0×10^{-10} mbar to 5.2×10^{-10} mbar. Impacting energies were $E_{i1}=3.36$ mJ and $E_{i2}=9.8$ mJ. Average pressure increases during impact obtained from several measurements were 1.9×10^{-10} mbar and 1.0×10^{-9} for the low and high energy impacts respectively. Small dispersion in amplitude of the initial pressure increase was observed when performing impacts on different surface zones of the same sample with the same indenter. We believe that this dispersion relates with changes of the indenter topography because of material transference from the sample to the indenter during impacts, as well as with a small dispersion of the impacting energies.

The pressure increase was mainly due to H_2 , although traces of mass 16 were also detected. Increases in ion currents due to H_2O^+ and CO^+/N_2^+ were at the detection limit of the mass spectrometer. The release of methane, which is neither adsorbed on the sample surface in UHV nor dissolved in the bulk of the stainless steel sample, should be assigned according to Repa [7] to a tribochemical induced reaction by the impact. Upper part of Fig. 2 shows the total pressure increase for the high energy impact as a function of time during and after impact. It can be observed that after a first sudden increase, just during impact, the pressure decreases slowly towards a residual stable pressure in approximately 10 s. The hydrogen ion

current recorded by the quadrupole mass-spectrometer as a function of time is shown in the lower part of Fig.2. Note that the shape is quite similar to the profile of the total pressure increase curve, although the ion current increase is more intense. A noticeable reduction of the pressure increase intensity was always observed after the first impact. The upper part of Fig. 3. shows the pressure increase corresponding to a sequence of impacts for the high energy impact. The lower part indicates the ion current increase of H₂. The observed increases over the intermediate times for both curves at impacts occurring at 5 and 100 min, can be assigned to the lack of reproducibility of the initial impacting site as a consequence of the vibrations produced by the vacuum pumps. The morphology of the surface at the impact region is shown in the micrography of Fig.4 corresponding to a high energy impact. The pattern is characterised by one big crater and several little ones around it. As discussed above the dispersion is due to the lack of reproducibility of the impacting site, with a maximum displacement of the centre of the impact of 0.9 mm. A more detailed view is shown at the right part of Fig. 4. It can be observed that material has been removed and transferred to the impacting ball. At the upper part of the crater an undulated structure can be observed. This structure is formed by a plastic deformation of the material of the substrate. The dimensions of the big crater are 0.86x1.00 mm and the small one has a diameter of 0.5 mm.

Recent investigations of hydrogen content in stainless steel [15] showed a non-uniform distribution of the dissolved hydrogen with depth. The highest concentration of 3.3×10^{22} at.cm⁻³ was observed near the surface, while it decreased to a constant value 6.10^{20} at.cm⁻³ at a depth of 1.7 μm. If we consider the plastic deformation as the main mechanism responsible for outgassing, the non-uniform hydrogen distribution in the bulk could explain the observed decrease of the outgassing rate after the first impact. During the first impact the surface layers, which are enriched in hydrogen, are involved in the observed intense plastic deformation with removing of material. As a result, the outgassing rate is higher. Upon subsequent impacts deeper layers of material with lower hydrogen content are

involved in the plastic deformation and the outgassing rate decreases. Another fact supporting this hypothesis is that after the second impact, the pressure peak intensity is almost constant, as corresponds to a constant hydrogen concentration at the deepest layers. Independence of the outgassing rate with time interval between impacts also indicates that the contribution of readsorption from the residual gas is negligible. Repa and Rott [7] reported a similar decrease of outgassing rate under friction of metals in UHV. It is interesting to note that in the experiments of Repa [7] the initial pressure increase was recovered after heating of the sample. The phenomenon can be explained on the basis of the mobility of hydrogen atoms dissolved in the bulk. Upon heating the hydrogen diffuses to the surface, increasing the concentration near the surface, so subsequent impact or friction will produce desorption rates of about the same intensity as the initial impact.

Another interesting experiment was performed to explain which mechanism is responsible for the observed outgassing under impact. Before performing any impact, the sample and indenter were exposed to deuterated water at 6×10^{-8} mbar pressure for 10 min, equivalent to 36 L exposure. Impact experiment of the sample was performed immediately after exposure and ion currents corresponding to masses 18, DO^+ , 19, HDO^+ and 20, D_2O^+ were recorded as a function of time during and after the impact. Deuterated water was used instead of regular water to avoid the influence of the undesirable residual H_2 pressure in the vacuum system. A set of runs showed that no increase at masses corresponding to DO^+ , HDO^+ and D_2O^+ was observed. Fig. 5 shows the result of the experiment at an impacting energy of 9.8 mJ. While the total pressure rose with similar shape as before and an intensity increase of 9.0×10^{-10} mbar, the intensities of the masses containing D atoms remained constant. Thus, it can be concluded that release of the H_2 dissolved in the bulk is the principal outgassing source under impact in UHV. Tribochemical induced reactions on the surface and the region of the bulk subject to the impact also contribute to the outgassing rate in the form of methane releasing, while mechanically stimulated desorption is negligible. Comparison of

our findings with that obtained by Repa et al. [7] for the case of friction allows us to conclude that surface plastic deformation is the main mechanism yielding outgassing under impact in UHV.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Experiments performed with stainless steel samples subjected to impact in UHV showed that release of gases dissolved in the bulk is the main outgassing mechanism. Hydrogen is the main desorbing species. Tribochemical reactions between carbon contaminants and adsorbed hydrogen taking place at the surface in contact contribute to the insignificant formation of CH₄. Mechanically stimulated desorption of adsorbed phases is negligible. Outgassing under impact is stimulated by intense plastic deformation of contact area. The leading role of plastic deformation in mechanically stimulated outgassing in UHV is present in most of modes of mechanical interaction as was reported in previous studies [2,7,9].

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References

1. Deulin E.A, Nevshupa R.A., de Segovia J.L. *Vacuum* 1999; 52(1/2):79.
2. Nevshupa R.A., de Segovia J.L., Deulin E.A. *Vacuum* 1999; 53:295-298.
3. Fujii Y, Ishimaru H. *J.Vac.Sci.Technol.* 1991; A 9(3):2017-2020.
4. Deulin E. A., Nevchoupa R. A., Peressadko A. G., et. al. "Development of system for diagnostics of mechanical elements of vacuum equipment" - Technical report №02.9.60000015. Moscow: BMSTU 1995; 90. (in Russian).
5. Peressadko A. G., Nevshupa R. A., Deulin E.A. (to appear in *Vacuum*)
6. Deulin E. A., Peressadko A. G. *Control and Diagnostics* 1998; 5:21-28. (in Russian)
7. Repa P, Rott M. *Vacuum* 1997; 48(7/9):775.
8. Repa P. *Vacuum* 1992; 43(5/7):367.
9. Repa P, Oralek D. *Vacuum* 1999; 53(1/2):299.
10. Repa P, Rott M. *Vacuum* 1997; 48(7/9): 745.
11. Gronych T, Peksa L, Repa P. *Vacuum* 1992; 43:689-692.
12. Repa P, Oralek D, Rott M, Gronych T, Peksa L. *Vacuum* 1995; 46 (8/10): 849-851.
13. Ishikawa Y, Yoshimura T. *J. Vac. Sci. Technol.* 1991; A 9(3):2021-2024.
14. Groszkowski J. *Bull. Acad. Pol. Sci.* 1961; 9:2.
15. Deulin E.A., Nevshupa R.A. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 1999; 144-145:283-286. Deulin E.A., Goncharov A.A., de Segovia J. L., Nevshupa R.A. *Surf. Interface Anal.* 2000; 30:635-637.

Figure captions

1. Schematic of the experimental set-up. The lever is welded to a flexible bellow and can rotate around the lever pin. It is mounted in two ball bearing devices, located on the atmosphere side (not shown). After removing the balance force the indenter falls down impacting with the sample surface. Energy of impact is controlled by the height of falling of mass center Δh .
2. Typical outgassing curve as a function of desorption time under impact of 9.8 mJ energy. Upper part: total pressure increase. Lower part: hydrogen ion current increase.
3. Outgassing under sequential impacts at the same surface zone. Between impacts the surfaces are exposed to 2×10^{-8} mbar residual pressure of the system, mainly hydrogen. Upper part : total pressure. Lower part: hydrogen ion current
4. Optical microphotography of the impacting zone. Right part is an enlarged view of the marked zone.
5. Outgassing after exposing the indenter and sample surface to D_2O at 6×10^{-8} mbar pressure for 10 min, equivalent to 36 L exposure.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4. R. Nevshupa, J.L.deSegovia

Fig. 5.

